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**HEALTH AND SOCIAL CHALLENGES EXPERIENCED BY OLDER INFORMAL
WORKERS IN URBAN SLUM COMMUNITIES AT CHENNAI**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the social and health concerns that older workers in the unorganised sector who live in Chennai City's urban slums face. These older informal workers are now more vulnerable due to rapid urbanisation, so a focused investigation into their lived experiences is required. The study employed a qualitative case study strategy and aims for 10 older workers who labour informally to offer an in-depth understanding of their everyday life and the contextual factors influencing their well-being. The data collected through participant observation and semi-structured interviews to provide rich, detailed descriptions of older workers' everyday life. This study aims to investigate the health issues that informal ageing workers face, including chronic illnesses, limited access to healthcare, and physical strain from their jobs; social and emotional issues, such as social exclusion, isolation, and lack of support from the community; coping mechanisms they use; the role that family and community support plays in reducing these issues; and strategies for enhancing their quality of life. According to thematic analysis, these workers frequently have long-term medical issues that are made worse by unfavourable working conditions and insufficient medical care. Their vulnerabilities are exacerbated by economic insecurity brought on by erratic income and a lack of social safety nets. Many people struggle with mental health issues, loneliness, and a sense of social invisibility. The study emphasised the critical need for focused interventions to improve the well-being and dignity of informal ageing workers in Chennai's urban slums, including better access to healthcare, more robust social support systems, and financial inclusion initiatives.

Keywords: - Informal Sector, Aging Workers, Urban Slums, Challenges

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INTRODUCTION

Aging is a normal phase of life, but it is greatly challenging particularly for those working in the informal sector, where social security, pensions, and medical benefits are severely restricted. In India, a substantial proportion of informal sector workers are still working well beyond traditional retirement age, mainly due to financial necessity. This reality is vividly apparent in the city slums of Chennai, a fast-developing metropolis, where aged men and women continue to find themselves in low-paying, arduous occupations like construction work, street vending, manual scavenging, laundry work, and domestic service. Their problems are exacerbated by adverse living conditions, inadequate access to quality care, and lack of economic stability. Ostracized by their socio-economic conditions, these aging workers in Chennai slums are particularly at risk of long-term health issues and psychological strain. With weak or no formal support structures within such communities, the majority have to manage on the basis of family or infrequent community support, which is rarely consistent. In most cases, these seniors have to endure all their several adversities by themselves, with precious little opportunity for decent aging in their setting. In spite of the large size of aged people in the unorganized sector, there is a significant lack of studies on their specific social and health concerns in the settings of urban slums. This research aims at fulfilling this gap by probing into the multifaceted realities faced by older informal workers in Chennai slums, assessing their coping strategies on a daily basis, and proposing measures to improve their well-being and quality of life.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kumar (2025) offers a conceptual framework for considering how marginality, social inequality, and gender inequalities increase vulnerabilities among the older population in urban India. The research underlines the increasing complexity of ageing in cities and emphasizes the effect of restricted group representation and entrenched social practices. Based on varied data, it emphasizes the necessity for community-led, culture-informed approaches to facilitate healthy ageing and overcome socio-economic problems at both institutional and residential levels.

Poulomi Chowdhury and Srinivas Goli (2024) point out that older informal workers in India encounter high out-of-pocket health costs because of the absence of insurance and social security. Employing LASI data, they demonstrate that such workers are more susceptible to catastrophic health expenditure and tend to keep working in old age to meet medical expenses. The study calls for universal health coverage and specific policies for the ageing informal workforce. Improving health care coverage and economic security may alleviate later-life economic disadvantage. This amplifies the need for inclusion in welfare policy among India's elderly informal workers.

Oteng, Amoah, and Huang (2024) undertook a systematic review on ageism against older informal workers and found that though they are perceived as experienced, they are excluded on the basis of low productivity and limited flexibility. Ageism negatively impacts their work participation and health. The research calls for specific policies and studies, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, to counter age-based discrimination in the informal economy.

Aboderin, Kano, and Owii (2017) point out that older people in sub-Saharan African slums are disproportionately left out of age-friendly cities (AFC) projects and slum health agendas. Their Nairobi research identifies critical health and social issues of older slum dwellers not captured by current AFC schemes. They call for localizing AFC indicators to capture local

priorities using participatory methods. The writers urge "age-friendly slums" programs to mainstream older persons into urbanization and healthy ageing policy.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Aging informal labourers in Chennai city slums are confronted with a myriad of interconnected and intricate issues that gravely impact their health, social integration, and economic security. In spite of their growing age and diminished physical strength, most of them are forced to persist in tough, poorly remunerated work because of the lack of pensions and financial instability. Chronic disease and declining physical health are prevalent but frequently untreated since good quality healthcare is financially or physically out of reach. Combined with these health issues are social isolation, exclusion from family or community events, and the psychological burden of living without much support. Financial need further exacerbates these factors since scarce savings and an inadequate comprehensive social security system increase their exposure. The integration of hard labour, social abandonment, and poor access to basic services begets a cycle of adversity that makes aging in urban slum life especially challenging for informal workers.

NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Targeting the condition of elderly informal workers in urban slums is important in order to develop effective, practical interventions and inclusive policies that respond to their specific needs. Current national policies and welfare programs tend to neglect the informal sector and many elderly slum dwellers do not receive proper support or protection. Since this vulnerable group is at increased risk as a result of compromised health, economic instability, and poor social networks, it is important that their situation be investigated in detail. This research aims to address this deficit by highlighting their living experiences, coping strategies, and support systems. In so doing, it offers useful lessons that can assist policymakers, non-governmental organizations, and healthcare practitioners in crafting context-relevant solutions and improving extant welfare programs. Finally, such focused attention is necessary to attain the dignity, security, and well-being of older informal workers, fostering social justice and equity in fast-growing urbanized regions such as Chennai.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To examine the health challenges faced by aging workers in urban slums, including chronic illnesses, access to healthcare, and work-related health concerns.
- To analyse the social and emotional challenges experienced by aging workers, including isolation, exclusion, and lack of community support.
- To explore the coping mechanisms adopted by aging workers in urban slums to manage their health and social challenges.
- To assess the role of community and family support in addressing the challenges faced by aging workers.
- To recommend strategies for enhancing the well-being of aging workers in Chennai's urban slums.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research uses a qualitative case study approach to understand the daily experiences and contextual factors that impact the well-being of ten elderly informal workers in urban slums in-depth. Purposive sampling was utilized in the selection of a wide variety of informal older workers, ensuring variation across gender, occupation, and locality. Data were gathered using

participant observation and semi-structured interviews, generating rich, detailed descriptions of their daily experiences. Thematic analysis was used to determine common themes and patterns representing the challenges, coping mechanisms, and support networks experienced by these older adults. It allows subtle perspective into the particular vulnerabilities and strengths of informal workers in these challenging urban settings.

MAJOR FINDINGS

From thematic analysis, the results synthesised patterns within the lived experiences of workers aged 60 years and older, with a focus on recurring themes of health difficulties, healthcare access, emotional and social challenges, coping strategies, accessible support systems, and approaches to well-being, in line with the study's aims.

Case Study 1

He was a 72-year-old tea stall attendant in Choolaimedu who endured chronic leg swelling and persistent pain from standing all day at his workplace. His engagement with healthcare was minimal; he primarily used painkillers bought from nearby shops, as formal health facilities were financially and geographically inaccessible. Following his wife's passing, he felt profoundly isolated, as younger colleagues seldom spoke to him. To cope, he took regular breaks, applied homemade herbal oil to his legs, and found comfort in conversations with friends at a nearby temple. Occasionally, his son provided financial support, and neighbours assisted with basic errands when needed. He believed affordable medicines and a community healthcare centre would have greatly improved his health.

Case Study 2

She was a 63-year-old flower seller in Otteri who suffered daily backaches and shortness of breath due to constant exposure to dust and vehicle exhaust while stationed along a congested roadside. Hospital visits were cost- and time-prohibitive, so she relied on home remedies and over-the-counter medicines. Having relocated from her village years earlier, she often felt lonely, grieving the loss of her former community. She found solace in prayer and regular temple visits. Her daughter's weekly calls, bringing food and companionship, brightened her days. She strongly supported elderly meeting spaces in her area and hoped for frequent health camps to address the health needs of older citizens.

Case Study 3

He was a 68-year-old cycle mechanic in Choolaimedu whose deteriorating eyesight and trembling hands made his job increasingly challenging, particularly later in the day. He couldn't afford regular medical check-ups, and free medical camps were rare in his neighbourhood. Socially, younger colleagues overlooked him, though a few long-standing customers respected him. To cope, he limited himself to lighter tasks, rested adequately, and practised basic meditation. Occasionally, an NGO in his area provided health checks and care, for which he was grateful. He suggested that NGOs offer regular eye tests and health services for older people in his community.

Case Study 4

She was a 70-year-old domestic worker in Kannagi Nagar who suffered from arthritis that restricted her ability to clean houses or perform strenuous tasks. Accessing clinics was difficult due to distance, so she relied on over-the-counter pain balms and occasional free medical drives. Socially isolated and excluded from community activities by younger workers, she coped by resting more frequently and using hot water bottles to ease pain. Although her son was often unavailable due to work, neighbourhood children occasionally helped with small chores and errands. She hoped for a pension scheme and active elder support groups in her locality to address these issues.

Case Study 5

He was a 74-year-old scrap collector in Saidapet whose job, involving heavy lifting, caused chronic backaches and persistent coughing. Unable to afford losing income, he continued working despite his health issues. The cost of formal healthcare forced him to rely on pills purchased from street vendors. He faced social exclusion due to the stigma associated with his work. To cope, he sang to himself while working and took long walks to relieve stress. Occasionally, he shared meals with an old fellow collector, his primary friend and confidant. He wished for cleaner, safer workplaces and periodic free health checks for workers like him.

Case Study 6

She was a 66-year-old garment cutter in Chintadripet who experienced frequent finger joint pain and occasional vision loss, impairing her ability to work. Doctor visits were costly, so she delayed treatment until absolutely necessary. She felt misunderstood by younger clients and increasingly disconnected from her tailoring peers. To manage, she took on less demanding tasks and used a magnifying glass for fine work. Her daughter helped with grocery shopping, and a women's group once provided a loan to sustain her business. She recommended regular women's health camps and a community space for older people to connect and support one another.

Case Study 7

He was a 69-year-old cobblestone layer in Nungambakkam, residing in Saidapet Slum, who suffered from severe knee and back pain, exacerbated during the monsoon season due to his physically demanding job. He rarely visited doctors, as a single consultation cost a day's wages, limiting his access to professional care. Both at work and home, he was largely isolated with little opportunity for social interaction. He managed with prescribed painkillers and home remedies prepared by his wife. Neighbours occasionally provided food or small loans during difficult times. He advocated for safer work equipment and health insurance schemes for informal workers like himself.

Case Study 8

She was a 64-year-old snack vendor in Pulianthope who developed varicose veins and swollen legs from standing for hours over the years. Nearby clinics were overcrowded, so she relied on herbal medicines and home remedies. After her husband's death and the relocation of many long-time friends, her sense of loneliness deepened. She coped by maintaining a consistent daily routine, retiring early, and finding emotional support in a self-help group.

Visits from relatives provided companionship. She suggested small business grants for older entrepreneurs and peer support groups for widows.

Case Study 9

He was a 73-year-old fruit vendor in Nungambakkam, living in Annanagar Slum, who suffered from persistent dizzy spells and untreated hypertension. The cost and time required for clinic visits deterred him, despite working in a busy, crowded environment that left him feeling emotionally detached. To cope, he shortened his workday, stayed hydrated, and listened to talk radio for comfort and a sense of companionship. His nephew occasionally assisted with deliveries, and kind customers offered help. He strongly advocated for more accessible health clinics with hours suitable for working older adults.

Case Study 10

She was a 70-year-old washerwoman in Royapuram whose hands were cracked and infected from years of exposure to water and harsh detergents. With limited finances, she rarely purchased medical ointments or visited clinics. She felt insecure about her job as many customers switched to washing machines. She managed by applying ayurvedic oils to her hands and found solace in spiritual radio broadcasts. Her grandson's frequent visits provided companionship and help with small chores. She proposed skill development programmes for older women and dedicated elder care and support centres in her community.

These ten case studies offered an in-depth exploration of how older informal workers in Chennai's slums navigated interconnected health, social, and livelihood challenges, capturing their material needs and aspirations.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The outcomes of the case studies of aging informal workers in Chennai city slums indicate long-standing vulnerabilities across health, social, economic, and emotional areas. Chronic conditions like arthritis, respiratory problems, and visual disturbances afflict most of the respondents, but with rather inimical barriers to accessing healthcare. Excessive charges for private treatment and distances to public clinics usually lead to late treatment, the use of over-the-counter medication, or home remedies. Financial pressures oblige most to opt for daily income over medical care, worsening their medical conditions. These medical conditions are aggravated by pervasive experiences of social isolation and rejection. Severed family bonds and broken community networks, spurred by urban migration and changing family structures, render many seniors without consistent emotional or social support. These problems fuel solitude and emotional suffering among most of the participants.

Coping strategies are largely individualized and uncomplex. Most seniors draw on rest, religious rituals like prayer, and the occasional social encounter with peers in coping with their physical and emotional struggles. Formal supports are limited; few receive sporadic support from family or local neighbours, while availability of government welfare programs or NGOs is restricted by lack of knowledge and bureaucratic obstacles. Economic insecurity is widespread, with the majority of respondents persisting with physically demanding informal work because they lack pensions or regular incomes. The tension of pitting work against declining health, as well as the threat of going into debt to meet basic needs, is a unifying thread. Over these aggravating conditions, resilience and optimism are found to

permeate the group. Most have strong hopes for access to affordable health care, more secure social relationships, and decent income-earning possibilities suitable to their age and abilities.

These findings align with and extend previous research on aging in urban poverty, confirming how intertwined economic hardship, social fragmentation, and insufficient health infrastructure exacerbate vulnerabilities among older informal workers. The rapid urbanization and unstable living conditions characteristic of Chennai's slums further intensify these challenges and emphasize the need for context-specific interventions. This research highlights the pressing need for cross-cutting policies and programs that not only increase elder-sensitive healthcare access and streamline welfare benefit registration but also foster inclusive social networks and encourage age-relevant economic participation. Activating families, communities, NGOs, and policymakers into collective action is essential to enhance the well-being and dignity of elderly informal workers. Future studies ought to expand the scope to encompass varied settings and viewpoints in order to provide more holistic and efficient strategies.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of these findings, the recommendations that follow are proposed:

- Open local, age-friendly clinics and arrange periodical health camps for continuous health monitoring and chronic disease management.
- Deploy mobile health units and recruit community-based health workers to cover housebound or immobile elderly in slum localities.
- Establish community centers specifically for senior citizens in slums with opportunities for socialization, informal education, peer support, and mental health activities.
- Enhance knowledge and simplify the access process to government pension schemes; implement microfinance schemes and vocational training for older informal sector workers to supplement income security.
- Implement education outreach and sensitization programs on available welfare benefits, healthy aging strategies, and legal entitlements using formats accessible to low-literacy elders.
- Encourage family and community involvement through intergenerational activities, neighbourhood events, and group programs to decrease social isolation and enhance support networks.
- Collaborate with NGOs, local authorities, and the private sector to provide supplementary food, medicines, routine health check-ups, and emotional counselling to socially isolate older persons.
- Increase geriatric care centers and facilitate the establishment of affordable assisted living and home healthcare services for elderly people living in poor slum areas.
- Implement routine monitoring and evaluation of programs and interventions to keep them relevant and responsive to the changing needs of aging informal workers.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the complex, overlapping hardships experienced by informal aging workers in Chennai's urban slums, including deteriorating health, economic insecurity, and

pervasive social isolation. While many older adults exhibit remarkable resilience and continue to contribute productively despite chronic illness and adversity, the absence of robust institutional support and accessible healthcare exacerbates their vulnerability. Effective intervention calls for joint, multi-sectoral action—better elder-friendly health facilities, enhanced social safety nets, focused awareness programs, and channels for dignified income opportunities. Initiatives to promote inclusive community space, increase dedicated geriatric and assisted living facilities, and construct dialogue among government, NGOs, and community leaders are critical. Finally, placing the rights, health, and dignity of elderly informal workers at the forefront is core to developing a more just, empathetic, and sustainable urban vision for Chennai and other cities.

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